

Donor Properties of 1-Amidino- O-Alkylureas: Part XIV. 1-Amidino-O-Alkylurea bis (Biguanide) Cobalt(III) Complexes

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A series of 1-amidino-O-alkylurea bis (biguanide) cobalt(III) complexes have been synthesised by the action of 1-amidino-O-alkylureas on diammine bis (biguanide) cobalt(III) base. Conductance and equivalent weights are reported. Electronic spectra reveal two ligand field bands around $28,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 21000 cm^{-1} . Resolution of the complex species has been effected through the fractionation of the chloride d-tartrate and d-camphor-10-sulphonate salts. Only the pure levo isomers have been isolated in good yield.

We are currently engaged in a study of mixed-ligand complexes, looking out for those complexes which are kinetically inert and could be processed for resolution into optically active antipodes¹. We describe herein the syntheses, characterisation and resolution of a host of 1-amidino-O-alkylurea bis (biguanide) cobalt(III) complexes.

The 1-amidino-O-alkylureas react readily with diammine bis (biguanide) cobalt (III) base with easy evolution of ammonia, resulting in the formation of the mixed chelates, $[\text{Co}(\text{AA})(\text{BigH})_2]^{3+}$ (AA=1-amidino-O-alkyl (methyl/isopropyl/isobutyl) urea and BigH=biguanide). These are all red to orange-red in colour and are obtained in crystalline form. A number of salts of the complex cations, namely the sulphate, chloride, iodide, cobaltinitrite, d-camphor-10-sulphonate and chloride-d-tartrate have been characterised. Conductance measurements in aqueous medium on the iodide salts provide values of tri-univalent electrolytes.² (Table I)

TABLE I
Conductance values in Aqueous solution at 20°.

Complex	Λ_M (ohms ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹)
1. $[\text{Co}(\text{AMUH})(\text{BigH})_2]\text{I}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	387
2. $[\text{Co}(\text{APIUH})(\text{BigH})_2]\text{I}_3$	385
3. $[\text{Co}(\text{ABiUH})(\text{BigH})_2]\text{I}_3$	389

AMUH=1-amidino-O-methylurea; APIUH=1-amidino-O-isopropylurea, ABiUH 1-amidino-O-isobutylurea

Following an ion-exchange technique³ the equivalent weights of the sulphate and chloride salts were also evaluated. (Table II)

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1. R. L. Dutta and S. Sarkar, *This Journal*, 1967, **44**, 832, 842, 853.

2. M. M. Jones, *Elementary Coordination Chemistry*, Prentice Hall, 1964, p 254.

3. R. L. Dutta and A. Syamal, *This Journal*, 1968, **45**, 115, 127.

TABLE II

Complex	Equivalent Weight	
	Found	Reqd.
1. [Co (AMUH) (BigH) ₂] (SO ₄) _{1.5} · 3.5H ₂ O	190	194
2. [Co (AMUH) (BigH) ₂] Cl ₃	165	160
3. [Co (AP ⁱ UH) (BigH) ₂] (SO ₄) _{1.5} · 3H ₂ O	204	200
4. [Co (AP ⁱ UH) (BigH) ₂] Cl ₃	172	169
5. [Co (AB ⁱ UH) (BigH) ₂] (SO ₄) _{1.5} · 1.5H ₂ O	192	196
6. [Co (AB ⁱ UH) (BigH) ₂] Cl ₃	178	174

The electronic spectra in aqueous solution are typical of octahedral cobalt(III) chelates⁴. Two ligand field bands around 28500 cm⁻¹ and 21000 cm⁻¹ representing the transitions ¹T_{2g} ← ¹A_{1g} (ν₂) and ¹T_{1g} ← ¹A_{1g} (ν₁) respectively, are observed. On comparing the values with tris(biguanide) cobalt(III), where the two bands appear around 28500 cm⁻¹ and 20900 cm⁻¹, little shifting is observed. Thus the 1-amidino-O-alkylureas set comparable ligand fields.

Resolution of the complexes has been effected through the formation of the diastereoisomeric salts with optically active anions. Treatment of the chloride salts with an excess of sodium d-tartrate furnished in all cases, on cooling for half an hour or so, a crystalline crop of the chloride d-tartrate which was further fractionated to yield the pure levorotatory diastereoisomer. Based on the weight of the starting amount of the mixed chelate, the levorotatory crops accounted for 40-50% of the chloride d-tartrate so that these are not cases of asymmetric transformation of the second order⁵. It was not possible to isolate

TABLE III

Electronic Spectra of Cobalt(III) mixed Chelates in Aqueous solution

Complex	Band II, cm ⁻¹ (ε)	Band I, cm ⁻¹ (ε)
1. [Co (AMUH) (BigH) ₂] ³⁺	28670-28200 (202)	21000 (210)
2. [Co (AP ⁱ UH) (BigH) ₂] ³⁺	28670-28200(213)	21000-20800(216)
3. [Co (AB ⁱ UH) (BigH) ₂] ³⁺	28670-28200 (162)	21000-20800 (190)
4. [Co (AEUH) (BigH) ₂] ³⁺	28100 (210)	21100 (225)
5. [Co (BigH) ₃] ³⁺	(a) 28600 (187)	21000-20800 (207)
	(b) 28600-28100 (220)	21000 (235)

Complexes 1,2,3, and 5(a) were measured as their sulphate salts and the rest as chloride salts.

the dextro isomer in reasonable optical purity due presumably to a high solubility. The fractional crystallisation of the 1-amidino-O-methylurea bis (biguanide) cobalt(III) d-camphor-10 sulphonate diastereoisomers provided both the levo and dextro fractions, although the rotation values appeared lower. Here, too, the levo separated before the dextro. Purification of the fraction appeared quite difficult. Attempts towards obtaining the dextro-complex iodide by trituration of the camphorsulphonate salt with KI or NaI brought about complete racemisation. The pure levo rotatory chloride d-tartrate

4. F. A. Cotton and G. Wilkinson, *Advanced Inorganic Chemistry*, Interscience, 1967, p. 875.

5. P. Rây and N. K. Dutt, *This Journal*, 1941, **18**, 289; 1943, **20**, 81.

diastereoisomer on treatment with saturated aqueous ammonium sulphate gave the pure levo complex sulphate. Both the diastereoisomer and the pure active complex sulphates are perfectly stable in aqueous solution at 25°. The samples suffered no loss of optical activity at 120° in the solid state. A comparison of our results with those of tris(biguanide) cobalt(III) reveals that a slightly higher asymmetry is set by the replacement of one of the biguanides by an amidino-O-alkylurea. Such replacements, however, do not change the sign of rotation of the less soluble diastereoisomers.

TABLE IV

Comparison of $[\alpha]_D$ and $[M]_D$ values of Related complexes

Compound	Temp°C	$[\alpha]_D$	$[M]_D$	Reference
1. 1[Co (BigH) ₃] (SO ₄) _{1.5} 3.5H ₂ O	31	-362.5	-2062	Rây & Dutt
2. 1[Co (AMUH) (BigH) ₂] (SO ₄) _{1.5} 3H ₂ O	25	-408	-2300	This Study
3. 1[Co (AP ⁱ UH) (BigH) ₂] (SO ₄) _{1.5} 3H ₂ O	25	-350	-2100	„
4. 1[Co (AB ⁱ UH) (BigH) ₂] (SO ₄) _{1.5} 2H ₂ O	25	-350	-2100	„
5. 1[Co (AEUH) (BigH) ₂] (SO ₄) _{1.5} 3H ₂ O	27	-375	-2200	Dutta & Sarkar

Due to the limited accuracy in the polarimetric measurements $[M]_D$ values have been given in round figures.

EXPERIMENTAL

Diammine bis (biguanide) cobalt(III) base monohydrate was prepared by following published procedures¹. Syntheses of the 1-amidino-O-alkylureas as sulphates and chloride have been described earlier in this series.⁶ Biguanide acid sulphate was prepared according to standard procedure⁷.

Most of the following complexes are soluble in water but insoluble in alcohol and acetone. The iodide and the d-camphor sulphonate salts have reasonable solubility in water, alcohol and acetone. The samples were airdried.

1-Amidino-O-methylurea bis (biguanide) cobalt(III) sulphate: Diammine bis(biguanide) cobalt (III) base (1.2 g) and 1-amidino-O-methylurea sulphate (0.6 g) were mixed with water (15 ml) and heated on a steam bath until evolution of ammonia ceased. The mixture was then cooled and neutralised with 2N H₂SO₄. The orange product was further purified by recrystallisation from hot water.

1-Amidino-O-methylurea bis(biguanide) cobalt (III) chloride: This was obtained by following a similar procedure using 1-amidino-o-methylurea chloride and 2N HCl during neutralisation.

The iodide, d-camphorsulphonate and chloride d-tartrate salts were prepared by metathetic reaction of the chloride with a concentrated solution of KI, neutralised d-camphorsulphonic acid or sodium d-tartrate. The cobaltinitrite salt was prepared by double decomposition of the sulphate with a solution of sodium cobaltinitrite.

6. R. L. Dutta and P. Rây, *This Journal*, 1959, **36**, 499.

7. D. Karipides and W. C. Fernclius, *Inorg. Synth.* vol. **7**, 57.

(±) 1-*Amidino-O-methylurea bis(biguanide) cobalt(III) chloride d-tartrate*: The chloride salt-(3 g) was dissolved in hot water (25 ml) and treated with a saturated solution of sodium d-tartrate (10 ml). The mixture was allowed to cool in an ice bath for half an hour, the crystals collected and washed with spirit.

(—) 1-*Amidino-O-methylurea bis (biguanide) cobalt(III) chloride d-tartrate*: The above salt (3.0 g) was dissolved in water (200 ml) and allowed to evaporate at room temperature under a fan. The first crop of crystals collected after thirty hours was levorotatory. The next few crops were levorotatory too. The last crop (when the entire mass was practically dried up) gave a poor levorotation. The substance is quite stable optically. It becomes anhydrous at 120° and the anhydrous salt shows comparable activity in solution. An aqueous solution left for months at room temperature did not show any appreciable change in rotation [α]_D²⁵ = -375°; [M]_D = - 2400°.

(—) 1-*Amidino-O-methylurea bis (biguanide) cobalt(III) sulphate*: A solid sample of the (—) chloride d-tartrate was triturated with a saturated solution of ammonium sulphate and allowed to stand for an hour. The crystals were filtered, washed with ice-cold water and then with acetone. This is also optically stable; [α]_D²⁵ = -408°; [M] = -2300°.

TABLE V

Characterisation data of the Cobalt(III) complexes

	% Co	% N	% Anion	[α] _D
1. [Co (AMUH) (BigH) ₂] (SO ₄) _{1.5} 3.5H ₂ O	Found : 9.9 Reqd : 10.1	33.8 33.6	24.5 24.7	
2. [Co (AMUH) (BigH) ₂] Cl ₃	Found : 12.3 Reqd : 12.2	40.9 40.7	22.3 22.1	
3.(±) [Co (AMUH) (BigH) ₂] Cl d-tart4H ₂ O	Found : 9.3 Reqd : 9.2	30.4 30.6	5.8 5.55	-150°
4. (-) [Co (AMUH) (BigH) ₂] Cl d-tart4H ₂ O	Found : 9.4 Reqd : 9.2	30.4 30.6	5.4 5.55	-375°
5. (-) [Co (AMUH) (BigH) ₂] (SO ₄) _{1.5} 3H ₂ O	Found : 10.4 Reqd : 10.2	34.4 34.2	25.1 25.1	-408°
6. [Co (AMUH) (BigH) ₂] I ₃ H ₂ O	Found : 7.8 Reqd : 7.6	25.4 25.3	50.5 50.0	
7. (±) [Co (AMUH) (BigH) ₂] (CS) ₃ 2H ₂ O	Found : 5.5 Reqd : 5.3	17.5 17.7	—	-100°
8. [Co (AMUH) (BigH) ₂] [Co(NO ₂) ₆] 3H ₂ O	Found : 15.2 Reqd : 15.4	36.7 36.6	—	
9. [Co (AP ⁱ UH) (BigH) ₂] (SO ₄) _{1.5} 3H ₂ O	Found : 9.9 Reqd : 9.8	32.4 32.6	24.0 23.9	
10. [Co (AP ⁱ UH) (BigH) ₂] Cl ₃	Found : 11.7 Reqd : 11.5	38.7 38.5	21.1 20.9	
11. [Co (AP ⁱ UH) (BigH) ₂] I ₃	Found : 7.7 Reqd : 7.5	24.9 25.0	48.3 48.5	
12. (±) [Co (AP ⁱ UH) (BigH) ₂] Cl d-tart4H ₂ O	Found : 9.1 Reqd : 8.9	29.8 29.7	5.2 5.3	-100°
13. (-) [Co (AP ⁱ UH) (BigH) ₂] Cl d-tart4H ₂ O	Found : 9.1 Reqd : 8.9	29.7 29.7	5.0 5.3	-325°
14. (-) [Co (AP ⁱ UH) (BigH) ₂] (SO ₄) _{1.5} 3H ₂ O	Found : 10.0 Reqd : 9.8	32.8 32.6	24.2 23.9	-350°
15. (±) [Co (AP ⁱ UH) (BigH) ₂] (CS) ₃ 2H ₂ O	Found : 5.0 Reqd : 5.1	17.4 17.2	—	-100°

Table V (Contd.)

	%Co	%N	%Anion	$[\alpha]_D$
16. [Co (AP ⁱ UH) (BigH) ₂] [Co(NO ₂) ₆] 4.5H ₂ O	Found :	14.6	34.0	—
	Reqd :	14.4	34.1	
17. [Co (AB ⁱ UH) (BigH) ₂] (SO ₄) _{1.5} 1.5H ₂ O	Found :	10.0	33.6	24.2
	Reqd :	10.0	33.3	24.4
18. [Co (AB ⁱ UH) (BigH) ₂] Cl ₃	Found :	11.4	37.4	20.6
	Reqd :	11.2	37.4	20.3
19. [Co (AB ⁱ UH) (BigH) ₂] I ₃	Found :	7.4	24.8	48.0
	Reqd :	7.3	24.5	47.7
20. (±) [Co (AB ⁱ UH) (BigH) ₂] Cl d-tart 5H ₂ O	Found :	8.7	28.4	5.1
	Reqd :	8.5	28.5	5.1
21. (-) [Co (AB ⁱ UH) (BigH) ₂] Cl d-tart 4.5H ₂ O	Found :	8.8	28.9	5.4
	Reqd :	8.6	28.7	5.2
22. (-) [Co (AB ⁱ UH) (BigH) ₂] (SO ₄) _{1.5} 2H ₂ O	Found :	10.0	32.5	24.1
	Reqd :	9.8	32.6	24.1
23. (±) [Co (AB ⁱ UH) (BigH) ₂] (CS) ₂ 2.5H ₂ O	Found :	5.1	17.1	—
	Reqd :	5.0	16.9	—
24. [Co (AB ⁱ UH) (BigH) ₂] [Co (NO ₂) ₆]	Found :	14.0	33.2	—
	Reqd :	14.0	33.2	

CSH=d-camphorsulphonic acid; d-tart=d-tartrate anion

In all the compounds hydration contents were determined by loss at 120°, which confirmed the formula given. For brevity the results have not been included in the Table.

Fractionation 1-amidino-O-methylurea bis (biguanide) cobalt(III) d-camphorsulpho-nate: The diastereoisomeric substance gives substantial levo rotation. An attempt to resolve the compound by slow crystallisation showed normal behaviour, producing the levo isomer as less soluble fraction. But the rotation of both the fractions were poor ($[\alpha]_D^{25} = \pm 150^\circ$).

All other complexes were obtained by following similar procedure. The relevant characterisation data appear in Table V.